

Integration of **Geodetic** and **imAging**
TecHniques for monitoring and
modelling the **Earth's** surface
defo**Rmations** and **Seismic** risk

Deliverable 6.3

COMMUNICATION GUIDE

WROCLAW UNIVERSITY
OF ENVIRONMENTAL
AND LIFE SCIENCES

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA

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Abbreviations

C	CDM	Communication and Dissemination Manager
E	EB	Executive board
	ENS	École Normale Supérieure (in French)
	ESAB	External Scientific Advisory Board
G	GA	General Assembly
	GATHERS	Integration of Geodetic and imAging TecHniques for monitoring and modelling the Earth's surface defoRmations and Seismic risk
I	IGf-PAN	Instytut Geofizyki – Polskiej Akademii Nauk (in Polish) for Institute of Geophysics – Polish Academy of Sciences
M	MM	Meeting minutes
	MST	Management Support Team
N	NOA	National Observatory of Athens
P	PC	Project Coordinator
	PW	Politechnika Warszawska (in Polish) for Warsaw University of Technology
Q	QM	Quality Manager
T	TM	Technical Manager
	TU Delft	Technische Universiteit Delft (in Dutch) for Delft University of Technology
	TU Wien	Technische Universität Wien (in German) for Vienna University of Technology
	TX.Y	Task number X.Y (X – WP number, Y – task number within WP)
U	UPWr	Uniwersytet Przyrodniczy we Wrocławiu (in Polish) for Wrocław University of Environmental and Life Sciences
W	WAT	Wojskowa Akademia Techniczna (in Polish) for Military University of Technology
	WP	Work Package
	WPL	Work Package Leader

1 Introduction

In the context of project organisation and program management, communications are a core competency that, when properly executed, connects every member of the project team to a common set of strategies, goals and actions. Unless these components are effectively shared by project leads and understood by stakeholders, project outcomes are jeopardised and budgets incur unnecessary risk.

2 Internal Communication

2.1 Email

The main communication channel to be used between the GATHERS partners will be the e-mail in order to keep the relevant information registered in a traceable mean. After every meeting, which will be done in person or via other communication tools, a meeting minutes will be prepared by the member of the Project Executive Board containing the meeting major discussion points, conclusions and the actions to be done in the upcoming days. The meeting template consists of the following format (Table 1):

Table 1. Meeting minutes template

Meeting Title				Location		
Date	DD.MM.YYYY	Meeting Start	XX:XX	Meeting Finish	XX:XX	
Attendees						
Item No	Subject	Discussion Points		Action	Responsible	Deadline

2.2 Slack

To avoid excessive spamming via email, for the daily task management, the Project EB (Executive board) is also using Slack (<https://slack.com/>) – a modern, cloud-based team communication and team collaboration messaging platform, where all the activities are divided into subgroups gathered around particular subject:

- # gathers_all – main channel for all participants with general information
- #wp1_management_team – a channel dedicated to the general management information sharing
- #wp2_insar – a channel dedicated to the task organisation and communication within WP2 “Early Stage Researchers training in Satellite Radar Interferometry (InSAR)”
- #wp3_lidar – a channel dedicated to the task organisation and communication within WP3 “Early Stage Researchers training in Laser scanning (LiDAR)”
- #wp4_gnss – a channel dedicated to the task organisation and communication within WP4 “Early Stage Researchers in GNSS seismology”

- #wp5_knowledge_integr – a channel dedicated to the activities and tasks within WP5 “Knowledge integration”
- #wp6_communication_team – a channel dedicated to the communication issues

Slack allows also to distribute files and send direct messages to the members, allowing using email only for important project communication.

2.3 Contact lists

The following contact email lists are generated to help in communication process:

- **General Assembly:** Consists of at least one representative of each Partner participating in the GATHERS project. A General Assembly meetings are done once a year;
- **Work Package Leaders:** GATHERS project is structured in 6 WPs, each work package has a leader (WPL) (Table 2). Each WPL has the task of presenting the status and progress of their individual WP to the Manager Support Team (MST) and report feedback to the participants of their own WP. They are responsible for the management and technical coordination of their WP on a daily basis and they translate decisions of the MST into daily (management) tasks, organise call meetings with the WP participants when necessary and report results and potential critical issues to the MST. The list of WP Leaders is presented below:

Table 2. List of Work Package Leaders

Participant Name	Participant Entity	Role
Maya Ilieva	UPWr	PC and WP1, WP5 and WP6 Leader
Ramon Hanssen	TU Delft	WP2 Leader
Norbert Pfeifer	TU Wien	WP3 Leader
Mattia Crespi	SAPIENZA	WP4 Leader

- **Management Support Team:** The Management Support Team (MST) consists of the Project Coordinator and Technical Manager (Dr. Maya Ilieva), the Administration & Finance Manager (Dr. Katarzyna Kopańczyk), the Quality manager (Dr. Grzegorz Jóźków), the Communication and Dissemination Manager (DI Carina Brachner) and the Innovation & Data Manager (Prof. Witold Rohm). A weekly meeting is done by the MST in order to stay up to date with the project progress;
- **Project Executive Board:** The Executive Board of GATHERS includes the coordinator and the Work Package Leaders . A monthly meeting is done to coordinate the interaction between the WPs strategies, monitor progress, advice and decide on major WP revisions, exchanges of tasks & budgets, intellectual property, dissemination strategies, communication, interaction with other activities and political issues. A project management template (see Annex 1: Project Management Template) containing an executive summary and the project status is sent by the Technical Manager to the WP Leaders and rest of the Management Support Team.
- **External Scientific Advisory Board (ESAB):** This board is formed of Prof. Beata Orlecka-Sikora (IGF-PAN, Poland), Prof. Pierre Briole (ENS, France), Prof. Athanassios Ganas (NOA, Greece), Prof.

Mariusz Figurski, Prof. Janusz Bogusz (WAT, Poland), PhD Krzysztof Bakuła (PW, Poland). ESAB advises and reports to the MST on issues regarding project strategy and optimization of applicability and exploitation of the results of the project.

In order to easily identify and classify the emails, they will have to contain the following “Subject”

Format: **[GATHERS-Scope-Description]**

- Scope: Code to identify the main aim of the communication. The following Codes for the Scope will be used:
 - GA: issues related to the General Assembly
 - EB: issues related to the Project Executive Board
 - MST: issues related to the Management Support Team
 - DX.Y: issues related to deliverable X.Y
 - TX.Y: issues related to Task X.Y
 - AD: Administration
 - O: other issues related to the project
- Description: small clear and concise description of the topic of the email.

Eg: Email to be sent to the General Assembly of the organisation of the Annual Meeting. The subject would be: [GATHERS-GA-Annual Meeting: Organization&Logistics]

2.4 Meetings' organisation

Meetings are organised by the members of Project EB face to face and whenever needed in audio-videoconferences through online tools like dedicated Whereby channel. In order to fix the date and time, *TERMINO* – the standard poll tool used at TU Wien (<https://www.termino.gv.at/meet/de>) which is similar to *doodle* - should be used, so that each participant could give their time availability. Once obtained the result, the optimal period is chosen so that maximum number of participants could participate. As stated above, after each meeting, minutes using the template (Table 1) is prepared and shared to through email.

2.5 EMDESK Project Management platform

The project management platform EMDESK is used to organise and control all the issues related with the GATHERS project execution. All partners have access to the EMDESK GATHERS project. It consists of the main project file repository, budget control tool, project progress control tool, project Gantt chart and schedule. It helps the MST with the daily project management.

2.6 Internal Communication Guide

In order to facilitate the usage of the internal communication, a short guide with information about the usable internal channels is created as part of the Communication Pack (D6.4). The entire internal communication data is summarised in Figure 1, showing details about the mailing lists, the vision of the Internal Communication Guide and including a hyperlink to the document repository in EMDesk project platform.

Figure 1. Internal Communication Guide at one glance

INTERNAL COMMUNICATION GUIDE at one glance

- For internal communication ...
 - ... **mailing lists** have been created:

GATHERS management team:	gathers_mgmt@list.tuwien.ac.at
GATHERS communication team:	gathers_comm@list.tuwien.ac.at
GATHERS whole consortium:	gathers_all@list.tuwien.ac.at
 - ... **a communication platform** (chat) **SLACK** has been set up and should be used for reducing mails and discussing project relevant topics. Chatrooms for each Work Package have been created.

gathersworkspace.slack.com
- Document sharing platforms: EM desk, owncloud
- For TeleCons use **whereby.com/gathers**

For communication within the consortium please use the following tools:

MAILING LIST:	gathers_all@list.tuwien.ac.at
CHAT PLATFORM:	gathersworkspace.slack.com
WORK SPACE:	https://app.emdesk.com
TELE CONS:	whereby.com/gathers

contacts

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download:
<https://gathers.emdesk.com/#!/documents/direct/d612>

3 External Communication

3.1 Webpage & Blog

The project website – www.gathers.eu – will be released in April 2020 (M5 of the project). It is the main interface towards all stakeholders interested in GATHERS, its progress, workshops, summer schools and its results.

The web site offers an integrated blog, on which projects, news and other project relevant content will be published and discussed.

The layout of the web page is based on an easy-to-use structure (see screenshot below – Figure 2) via WordPress and integrated in project colour scheme.

3.2 Social media

Social media communication and dissemination helps increasing GATHERS impact and reach a wider audience. The main social media channels used for the project are Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Youtube.

These channels are being used to:

- Create public interest in the project;
- Attract visitors to the GATHERS webpage and project content;
- Sharing information and outcomes of the project;
- Spread the news about activities in different countries;
- Connecting partners, students, stakeholders, etc., and building relationships (also to other related projects);
- Announcing and advertising specific events related to the project (content).

The frequency of tweets and postings depends on deliverables, events and project outcomes. Especially in the first months there will be more postings to draw attention to the project and its goals.

3.2.1 Twitter

Twitter is an information network/system that allows to post short messages called tweets. A tweet can be up to 140 characters long and can include links to relevant websites and resources.

The GATHERS twitter account can be found under @GATHERS_EU and was customised with the project identity (https://twitter.com/GATHERS_EU).

The hashtags used for the project are #GATHERS, #GATHERS_EU. Using further hashtags like #H2020, #HORIZON2020, #TWINNING, etc., to show the funding and connection with other H2020 projects is recommended.

In addition, tagging with @EU_H2020 and @REA_RESEARCH relevant postings is also advised.

Figure 2. Screenshot of the main page of GATHERS web-site

3.2.2 Facebook

Facebook is a social networking platform which allows users to upload photos and videos, share links and connect with their community.

A GATHERS Facebook page has been created: <https://www.facebook.com/gathersEU>
It will be maintained by students and supervised by the communication and dissemination manager of the project.

Facebook will be mainly used for creating and promoting events, as well as informing the network about important milestones in the project. The GATHERS Facebook page directs to the main website of the project.

3.2.3 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social network that focuses on professional networking and career development. The GATHERS LinkedIn account is mainly aimed at companies, stakeholders, scientists and business enterprises and serves to extend the scope of the project.

It can be found under the name GATHERS project (or <https://www.linkedin.com/in/gathers-project-84b6281a1/>)

3.2.4 Youtube

Youtube is a video sharing platform, where registered users can watch, share, like, comment and upload their own videos. The GATHERS Youtube channel will be used for sharing and collecting videos which have been created as part of the project. The project account can be found under the name @GATHERS_EU (or https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCObYkSdjLWwtG0GgRI_jMTA).

3.3 Brochure, Roll-ups and Posters

GATHERS foresees the creation of friendly material that encourages the audience to get familiar/up to date with the project:

- Brochure (x4) Posters (x3): will be shown in sectorial conferences and events. Containing the main results obtained by the project for specific user types;
- Official project Roll-up's (x1) designed with GATHERS project identity colours.

3.4 External Communication Guide

Similar to the summarised presentation of the internal communication information, showed above in 2.6, an External Communication Guide is prepared as part of the Communication Pack (D6.4). In, showing details about the mailing lists, the vision of the External Internal Communication Guide and including a hyperlink to the document repository in EMDesk project platform.

Figure 3. External Communication Guide at one glance

EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION GUIDE Summary

Project webpage: gathers.eu

GATHERS on social media:

GATHERS

**GATHERS
SOCIAL MEDIA
COMMUNICATION GUIDE**

Follow us on:

 [@gathersEU](https://facebook.com/gathersEU)

 [@GATHERS_EU](https://youtube.com/GATHERS_EU)

 gathers.eu

USE THE FOLLOWING #HASHTAGS RELATED TO THE PROJECT:

**#GATHERS #GATHERS_EU #H2020 #HORIZON2020
#TWINNING @EU_H2020 @REA_RESEARCH**

 TU WIEN TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN

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- Facebook: [@gathersEU](https://facebook.com/gathersEU)
- Twitter: [@gathers_eu](https://twitter.com/gathers_eu)
- LinkedIn: [GATHERS Project](https://linkedin.com/company/gathers-project)
- Youtube: [@GATHERS_EU](https://youtube.com/GATHERS_EU)

When posting project news be sure to use (at least one of) the following hashtags:

**#Gathers #GathersEU #Gathers_eu #H2020 #Horizon2020 #twinning #eu_h2020
#rea_research**

3.5 Use of EU's communication resources

GATHERS in communication activities will make use of the EU's freely accessible communication tools like (following the Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants, 2014):

Table 3. List of EU freely accessible communication tools

Tool and address	Description	Instructions
For Publications		
Horizon Magazine http://horizon-magazine.eu/	HORIZON is the EU Research & Innovation e-magazine. It is covering the latest developments in EU funded research and innovation, communicating the priorities and achievements of EU-funded research, its impact on citizens' lives and its contribution to the EU goals of smart and sustainable growth. It is written by independent journalists on behalf of DG Research & Innovation and is updated at least three times a week with new articles.	For story suggestions or questions to the editor, e-mail: RTD-PUBLICATIONS@ec.europa.eu
Project stories https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/newsroom/551/	Articles about selected EU-funded research projects, which led to breakthroughs, discoveries and world-firsts by taking great ideas from the lab to the market, at the same time contributing to economic growth and creating jobs, and tackling societal challenges.	Please contact your Project Officer about any interesting project outcomes. Furthermore, a journalist contracted by the European Commission may contact you.
research*eu results magazine https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/en	This print magazine features highlights from the EU-funded research and development projects. It is published 10 times per year in English, and covers mainly the research areas of biology and medicine, Social sciences and humanities, energy and transport, environment and society, IT and telecommunications, industrial technologies and space.	Please contact your Project Officer about any interesting project outcomes. Furthermore, a journalist contracted by the European Commission may contact you.

<p>Co-publications or editorial partnerships</p>	<p>The European Commission works with private publishers and international organisations to promote the dissemination of relevant publications. Scientific publications and books, including conference proceedings, may be co-published in this way.</p>	<p>Please contact your Project Officer to discuss the possibilities.</p>
<p>For Audio-visual contents</p>		
<p>Futuris Magazine https://www.euronews.com/programs/futuris</p>	<p>Short documentary-style television magazine in various languages, appearing at least 22 times on the EuroNews channel throughout Europe.</p>	<p>EuroNews has editorial independence, but we are in contact with them to suggest good stories. Since it is television, this is interesting for visually appealing projects and demonstration activities. Please contact your Project Officer if you would like your project to be put forward.</p>
<p>For events announcements</p>		
<p>Events on the Commission’s Research & Innovation website https://ec.europa.eu/research/index.cfm?pg=events</p>	<p>This website displays research and innovation-related conferences and events.</p>	<p>You can submit an event by using the “Suggest an event” functionality which is available on the left-hand side of the website.</p>
<p>Events on the CORDIS website www.cordis.europa.eu/news/home_en.html</p>	<p>This website displays research-related conferences and events.</p>	<p>Submitting an event requires one-time registration on the CORDIS website</p>
<p>Conferences and events organised by the European Commission</p>	<p>Throughout the year, the European Commission (co-organises a variety of conferences, both in Brussels and elsewhere. These may include exhibition areas or sessions at which you could present your work.</p>	<p>Please contact your Project Officer if you have suitable exhibition items (prototypes, demonstrators)</p>
<p>For Open access scientific publishing</p>		
<p>Open access scientific publishing Openaire www.openaire.eu</p>	<p>The Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe is an electronic gateway for peer-reviewed articles and other important scientific publications (pre-prints or conference publications).</p>	<p>You may submit your publications to www.openaire.eu</p>

For Online news		
<p>Online news Headlines on the Commission’s Research & Innovation website www.ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/all_headlines_en.cfm</p>	<p>Headlines report on recent developments in research and innovation in Europe and beyond and are devoted purely to projects. Suitable stories to be published on the site are selected on a daily basis.</p>	<p>You may submit your news (by means of a press release, event announcement or otherwise) via CORDIS wire http://cordis.europa.eu/wire/</p>
<p>CORDIS Wire http://cordis.europa.eu/wire/</p>	<p>CORDIS Wire provides registered users with a simple interface to publish articles on the CORDIS website’s News and Events service. All articles are moderated by CORDIS editors before publication.</p>	<p>Requires one-time registration at http://cordis.europa.eu/wire/</p>

4 Rules and obligation regarding EU Emblem and disclosure

All documents related to the GATHERS project (official templates, dissemination materials including the social media and the official website) must use the European emblem (flag) represented in Figure 4 to acknowledge the support received under EU programmes.

Figure 4. EU emblem

The emblem shall be associated to a disclosure sentence: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 857612”.

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Annex 1: Project Management Template

This template covers an example of the Monthly Project Report prepared by the Management Support Team to the Project Coordinator.

1. Executive Summary
2. Overall status of the project
3. Progress by WP (Progress status in previous month, Current progress, Deviation (explanation))
4. Important dates and activities for the coming months (detailed description)
5. Changes to the project scope and potential amendments suggestion to the Grant Agreement
6. Risk assessment: Threats and challenges for the coming period, Risk Management update
7. Performed activities during the reporting month:
 - a. DX.X finished
 - b. Brochure designed
 - c. Social media activities etc.

